

Indo-Soviet Cooperation (1971-1991): Strategic Alliances and Their Influence on Geopolitical, Economic, and Defense Relations

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Abstract

This research paper presents a comprehensive exploration of Indo-Soviet relations from 1971 to 1991, a period characterized by significant global political and non-political shifts. It delves into the intricate connections between diplomatic, economic, and cultural interactions that shaped this bilateral relationship within a transforming geopolitical environment. The years from 1971 to 1991 witnessed substantial changes, influenced by Cold War dynamics and the decolonization process. During this era, India and the Soviet Union developed a strategic partnership that was instrumental in shaping geopolitics in South Asia and beyond. The introductory chapter establishes the historical backdrop, pinpointing the key factors that led to the strengthening of ties between India and the Soviet Union during this period. It provides a detailed review of the historical progression of their relationship, from India's early post-independence years to the conclusion of the Cold War. The paper employs theoretical frameworks such as realism, alliance politics, and the balance of power to analyze this bilateral relationship. The contributions of prominent actors, including key leaders and diplomats, are examined to assess their roles in nurturing the partnership. Furthermore, the paper investigates the non-political facets of Indo-Soviet relations, such as economic cooperation, cultural interactions, and technological exchanges, illustrating how these aspects supported the political alliance and reinforced the overall strength of the relationship. By addressing both the political and non-political dimensions of Indo-Soviet ties, this research provides a nuanced understanding of a pivotal period in international relations, revealing the complex nature of the Indo-Soviet partnership and its lasting influence on regional and global affairs.

Keywords: *Indo-Soviet relations, Strategic partnership, Diplomatic intricacies, Economic and defense exchanges*

1. Introduction

1.1 Indo-Soviet Treaty of Friendship and Cooperation:

The Indo-Soviet Treaty of Friendship and Cooperation, signed in 1971, was a foundational document in this era. This treaty solidified the political alliance between India and the Soviet Union after the India-Pakistan war, emphasizing mutual support in the face of external threats. The Indo-Soviet Treaty of Friendship and Cooperation, an instrumental document signed in 1971, holds paramount historical significance, serving as a cornerstone in shaping the political landscape of that era. This treaty stands as a testament to the deepening political alliance between India and the Soviet Union, particularly in the aftermath of the India-Pakistan war, delineating a commitment to mutual support against external threats (Ganguly, 2002). The

genesis of this treaty can be traced back to the geopolitical dynamics of South Asia in the early 1970s. The India-Pakistan war in 1971, also known as the Bangladesh Liberation War, was a pivotal moment. India's involvement in this conflict, supporting the independence movement in Bangladesh, brought India and the Soviet Union closer together due to shared geopolitical interests and concerns. Signed on August 9, 1971, the Indo-Soviet Treaty of Friendship and Cooperation laid the groundwork for a multifaceted relationship between the two nations. It wasn't merely a diplomatic agreement but a comprehensive pact encompassing political, military, economic, and strategic facets.

1.2 Alignment in Global Forums:

Both nations collaborated extensively in global forums like the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM), advocating common positions on various international issues. This alignment showcased their shared perspectives and bolstered their political bond. The collaboration between India and the Soviet Union within global forums, notably the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM), stands as a significant testament to their shared diplomatic endeavors and the consolidation of their political alliance. This collaborative stance in international platforms such as the NAM not only demonstrated their unity but also fortified their political bond (Pant, 2009).

1.2.1 Differing Views on Afghanistan:

The Soviet intervention in Afghanistan in 1979 created a divergence in perspectives. While the Soviet Union intervened militarily, India maintained a stance against intervention, expressing concerns about regional stability. This differing view strained their political consensus. The Soviet intervention in Afghanistan in 1979 marked a significant turning point in the relationship between the Soviet Union and India. This intervention led to a notable divergence in perspectives between the two nations. While the Soviet Union opted for military intervention, India took a principled stance against such interference, expressing concerns primarily centered on regional stability. This divergence in views strained the political consensus between India and the Soviet Union (Sarin, 2013). The Soviet Union's decision to intervene in Afghanistan stemmed from various geopolitical concerns, including maintaining influence in the region and preventing potential threats to its interests. The military intervention aimed to stabilize a turbulent political situation in Afghanistan, but it was met with international condemnation and resistance.

1.3 Trade Dependency and Agreements:

India heavily relied on the Soviet Union for imports, particularly in defense, machinery, and technology. Bilateral trade agreements were signed to enhance economic cooperation, shaping the trade dynamics between the two nations. The economic and trade relationship between India and the Soviet Union from 1971 to 1991 constituted a pivotal aspect of their bilateral cooperation, characterized by mutual dependency and significant trade agreements. During this period, India's reliance on the Soviet Union for imports, especially in defense, machinery, and technology, was pronounced. Bilateral trade agreements played a crucial role in fostering and enhancing economic cooperation, ultimately shaping the trade dynamics between these two nations (Bhattacharya, 2009).

1.4 Aid and Economic Assistance:

Apart from trade, the Soviet Union provided economic aid and assistance to India in various sectors, contributing to India's economic growth and infrastructure development during this period. The period between 1971 and 1991 witnessed significant economic cooperation between India and the Soviet Union, reflecting a substantial facet of their multifaceted relationship. Apart from trade ties, the Soviet Union played a pivotal role in providing economic aid and assistance to India, contributing significantly to India's economic growth and infrastructure development (Singh, 2014). Soviet Assistance Programs: The Soviet Union extended economic aid and assistance to India across diverse sectors. This aid encompassed financial support, technological assistance, and expertise, fostering development in crucial areas such as industry, agriculture, and infrastructure.

1.5 Defense and Strategic Relationship:

The Soviet Union emerged as a primary supplier of military hardware to India, supplying tanks, aircraft, submarines, and other advanced weaponry. This extensive military cooperation significantly bolstered India's defense capabilities. The period from 1971 to 1991 witnessed a pivotal phase in the defense and strategic relationship between India and the Soviet Union, characterized by extensive military cooperation that significantly shaped India's defense capabilities. Central to this cooperation was the Soviet Union's emergence as a key supplier of military hardware to India, providing an array of advanced weaponry, including tanks, aircraft, submarines, and various other defense systems (Chaulia, 2012). The Soviet Union's role as a primary supplier of military equipment to India was a strategic move that deepened the bilateral relationship between the two nations. This collaboration wasn't merely transactional but marked a significant step in India's quest for bolstering its defense capabilities.

1.6 Strategic Support and Cooperation:

India received substantial strategic support from the Soviet Union in building defense infrastructure and technological advancements. This support played a pivotal role in shaping India's strategic positioning in the region. The period from 1971 to 1991 witnessed a robust defense and strategic relationship between India and the Soviet Union, marked by significant support and cooperation, which had a profound impact on India's defense capabilities and strategic positioning in the region. The assistance and collaboration provided by the Soviet Union played a pivotal role in shaping India's defense infrastructure and technological advancements, significantly enhancing its strategic prowess (Pant, 2009).

1.7 Cultural Exchanges and Collaborations:

Both nations fostered cultural exchanges encompassing film festivals, artistic collaborations, and academic interactions. These exchanges played a crucial role in strengthening people-to-people ties and mutual understanding. The period from 1971 to 1991 witnessed a profound cultural exchange and collaboration between India and the Soviet Union. This cultural synergy played a significant role in nurturing a deep bond between the two nations, transcending political and diplomatic realms. Through various initiatives like film festivals, artistic collaborations, and academic interactions, India and the Soviet Union fostered a vibrant

cultural relationship that contributed immensely to strengthening people-to-people ties and mutual understanding (Mukherjee, 2017). Film festivals were a cornerstone of the cultural exchange between India and the Soviet Union. Both nations hosted film festivals showcasing cinematic creations from their respective countries. These festivals served as platforms to celebrate the diversity and richness of each other's cinematic traditions, allowing audiences to experience and appreciate the cultural nuances embedded in the films.

1.8 Economic Reforms in India:

Post-1991, India underwent economic liberalization, reducing its reliance on Soviet aid and trade. This shift impacted the dynamics of the Indo-Soviet relationship, requiring adjustments in their engagements. The period between 1971 and 1991 witnessed a profound and dynamic Indo-Soviet cooperation, significantly impacted by the economic reforms India underwent post-1991. This era marked a crucial phase in their relationship, characterized by strategic alliances, economic cooperation, and political alignment. However, the advent of economic liberalization in India post-1991 brought about a paradigm shift that altered the dynamics of the Indo-Soviet relationship, demanding significant adjustments in their engagements (Panagariya, 2008).

2. Literature Review

Indo-Soviet Political relations

2.1 Indo-Soviet Camaraderie (1971-1980)

The deepening connection between India and the Soviet Union was notably evidenced by the substantial Soviet support for India's economic progress. An illustration of this is the significant surge in trade volume between the two nations over twenty years, from 1955 to 1974. During this time, trade escalated dramatically, soaring from 55 million to Rs.5,500 million by 1974. Moreover, this growth trajectory persisted, with total trade surpassing the Rs.700 million milestone in 1975. The official trade agreement was established in 1953, marking India's inaugural long-term pact with a foreign nation. The inclusion of provisions enabling clearance in Indian rupees and a self-balancing system, mandating both parties to bolster trade based on mutual needs, greatly fueled the dynamic expansion of Indo-Soviet trade (Government of India, Ministry of Defence (1969-1988).

During Brezhnev's 1973 visit to India, a comprehensive 15-year agreement was reached, revitalizing Indo-Soviet trade. This revitalization propelled trade volume from Rs.4,300 million in 1973 to Rs.6,500 million in 1974 (Government of India, Ministry of External Affairs, 1969-1987).

The proposed five-year trade agreement from 1976 to 1980 aimed to achieve a doubling in trade, fulfilling the aspirations of leaders such as Mrs Gandhi and Leonid Brezhnev. Enhancing trade with the Soviet Union presented notable advantages for India. It helped break away from the colonial trade dynamics with the capitalist world, where India was compelled to accept unfavourable prices for raw materials and pay excessively high costs for finished goods. This shift, primarily due to the emergence of the Soviet Union as a viable alternative market, significantly benefited India. Moreover, rupee trade evolved beyond a mere exchange of commodities, becoming crucial for India's foreign exchange challenges and facilitating balanced trade with the Soviet Union. Stability characterized the trade relationship, free from

the fluctuations experienced in capitalist economies due to the Soviet Union's planned economy. Imports and exports remained steady, unaffected by economic depressions that troubled capitalist nations. This diversification complemented the conventional exports (Government of India, Ministry of Finance, 1971-1987).

Fig. 1 Existing and proposed Indo-Russia trade route[Existing & Proposed Route]

Challenges of Indo-Soviet Relations (1970-1980)

Initially, the Soviet Union desired to cultivate joint economic ventures with the USA, implicitly recognizing the expanding capacity of the American economy. However, given the limited flexibility of the Soviet economy primarily tied to Comecon countries in trade, it became crucial for Moscow to explore areas where the Soviet economy could potentially expand and become more flexible. Among third world countries, besides India with its growing public sector and large population, seemed the most suitable partner for the Soviet Union.

The significant increase in Soviet-Indian trade over the past decade, quadrupling in volume, buoyed Soviet hopes for economic prospects in India. India had emerged as one of the USSR's main trade partners, holding a pivotal position in Soviet foreign trade programs. Notably, the production collaboration pacts inked in 1973 between India and the Soviet Union were noteworthy. These agreements dictated that the USSR would export raw materials to India, and the finished products would be marketed in the Soviet Union. For instance, Soviet cotton would be transformed into sewing threads and textiles, wool into knitwear, and steel into cutlery, nuts, and bolts, all to be exported to the Soviet Union. Therefore, Brezhnev emphasized that more than half of the Soviet Union's purchases in India comprised products from India's burgeoning industry (Novosti Press, 1971).

Seeking enhanced economic ties with India, the Soviet Union, through a fifteen-year trade and economic pact in December 1973, proposed improvements in credit terms, allowing for

extended grace and repayment periods. During Brezhnev's visit, a separate agreement formed a joint team comprising Soviet Gosplan and Indian Planning Commission members. This team aimed to streamline supply issues and enhance economic collaboration while facilitating the exchange of expertise in economic forecasting and planning methods. The Soviet Union motivated India to build its own heavy industrial complexes, such as the facility in Ranchi, aiming to reduce India's reliance on technologically advanced capitalist nations and foster indigenous design capabilities (Whelan, 1984).

Indo-Soviet Trade Relations during the Cold War Era

It was additionally highlighted that only a small number of joint ventures with the Soviet Union were fully executed, revealing the pressing issue of marketing that needed addressing. Many of these initiatives experienced underuse due to various reasons, such as inadequate planning by Indian authorities. An instance illustrating the marketing challenge in Soviet-supported projects emerged when the United States declined to purchase equipment from Ranchi's heavy machine building plant. Consequently, India was limited to exporting solely to the USSR. The suggestion was made that previously, the Soviets provided crucial machinery and equipment for diverse industries. However, the primary hurdle in enhancing trade between the nations stemmed from the inadequate coordination between them. For a developing nation like India, the challenge lay in aligning its production and trade strategies with the centrally planned economies. Failure to do so would inevitably lead to obstacles in securing the necessary imports. Hence, the major dilemma faced by a developing nation was finding a balance: benefiting from guaranteed sources of supplies and connected markets without becoming overly reliant on them (Vajpayee, 1978).

Fig. 2 Indo-Soviet Route via Ashgabat Agreement[[Ashgabat Agreement](#)]

Indo-Soviet Cooperation during the Emergency Period (1975-77)

The signing of a long-term trade agreement for 1976-80 in New Delhi during mid-April appeared to lack the previous enthusiasm typically associated with such events. According to Indian press reports, the subdued statements conveyed this sentiment during the occasion. It was noted that talks had commenced in 1974, followed by two rounds in 1975, and a Soviet trade delegation had worked on it in January and February 1976 (Bajpai, 1982). India's push to normalize relations with China prompted action from the Soviets, culminating in the 1976 accord with India. This marked a pivotal shift in India's economic ties with the Soviet Union early in 1976. There was a significant transformation in the volume and diversity of trade and the nature of collaboration. The agreement finalized in Moscow after Mr. Haksar's visit outlined plans for establishing new industries in India with Soviet support. The 1976-1980 trade agreement was negotiated within this broader framework. Prof. D.P. Chattopadhyaya, India's Commerce Minister, highlighted that this agreement would embody structural changes, serving as a robust catalyst for fostering bilateral trade growth. In this context, he mentioned the Soviet Prime Minister Kosygin's report to the 25th Congress of the CPSU. He highlighted the Soviet leadership's focus on broadening economic and trade ties with developing nations based on fair and democratic principles. The aim was to bolster the economic autonomy of these countries (Bhatia, 1984).

Indo-Soviet Trade and Defense Cooperation in the 1970s: Navigating Challenges and Strengthening Ties

During the early seventies, when oil prices soared and India faced continuous shortages, it had sought crude oil from the Soviet Union. Initially, Moscow declined sales to New Delhi, citing its domestic and East European consumption being almost equivalent to its production capacity. The reality, however, was that with oil becoming a lucrative commodity, Moscow prioritized regions that could provide hard currency. Despite offering kerosene and diesel fuel during the 1974 energy crisis, the Soviets refrained from selling crude oil until Grishin's announcement in December 1976. Grishin disclosed Moscow's readiness to provide crude oil on a long-term basis, proposing an exchange for Indian pig iron, which India had in surplus. The Soviet offer included 5.5 million metric tons of crude, with 0.1 million to be delivered in 1977 and 1.5 million annually for the next three years. This trade arrangement, swapping oil for pig iron, fueled optimistic projections that bilateral trade might hit the 1980 target as early as 1977. Furthermore, India was expected to receive approximately 7 to 10 percent of its crude oil imports from the Soviet Union without significant foreign exchange costs.

However, the challenge of diversifying Soviet exports to India, which partly hindered reaching the 1976 target, remained unresolved. Efforts were underway to acquire Soviet machinery and equipment for export-oriented coastal cement plants. Collaboration plans progressed, with contracts valued at approximately Rs.33.00 Crores signed for supplying Indian equipment to Soviet-aided steel and metallurgical projects in countries like Cuba, Turkey, and Bulgaria. Furthermore, a proposal was forming for India to manage the civil construction aspect of Soviet-aided projects in West Asia and elsewhere. The evolving industrial and commercial requirements of both countries presented new opportunities but complicated the coordination of needs and capacities (Dutt, 1984).

Fig. 3 Strategic land and sea Indo-Russia route[[Land & Sea](#)]

Following the setback of the 1962 conflict, India shifted towards prioritizing military modernization, reflected both in bureaucratic and political spheres. Indira Gandhi, shaped by this new approach, departed from Nehru's idealistic internationalism and embraced realpolitik and power dynamics, seeing them as vital for internal stability and India's global standing. Though elements of Nehru's idealism persisted in Indian diplomatic thinking during Indira Gandhi's tenure, they were significantly overshadowed by a more pragmatic approach. Moving away from Nehru's idealistic peace-focused diplomacy towards a more pragmatic approach rooted in military power, Mrs. Gandhi significantly enhanced India's military capabilities through modernization efforts, with substantial support from the Soviet Union. The Soviet connection played a pivotal role in strengthening India's armaments sector. With the Kremlin's strategic shift towards engaging with the Third World, providing arms became a tool for wielding political influence. The Soviet Union saw India's empowerment as a counterbalance to China, viewing the enhancement of Indian defense as advantageous to its own interests. This partnership not only bolstered India's defense but also cemented the Soviet Union's position in the region, fostering a mutual perception of aligned interests between the two nations. Consequently, the Soviet Union was willing to take the risk of sharing advanced military technology with India (George, Litwak, & Chubin, 1984).

Indo-Soviet Dynamics of Dependency and Diplomacy (1971-1977)

Following the 1971 Indo-Pakistan conflict, the Soviets rejected Indian appeals for advanced aircraft, leading Mrs. Gandhi to explore alternatives like the Anglo-French Jaguar. This resistance hinted at the Soviet reluctance to commit further to India in terms of sophisticated weaponry. During Brezhnev's 1973 visit to India, there was a deliberate avoidance of discussing arms trade, evident from the absence of any mentions in his speeches. Concerns were raised about the deficiencies in Soviet equipment, particularly regarding the performance of SU-7 bombers (Mishra, 1977). It was claimed that despite the initial affordability of Soviet

equipment, the subsequent costs for spare parts and additional necessary components were expensive, and their availability was uncertain. Additionally, the Soviet commitment to confidentiality hindered the complete exchange of technical expertise, which was vital for India's defense industry's future progress. There was clear evidence of a lack of substantial interaction between Russian instructors and Indian servicemen, whose connection was limited solely to technical training. Mrs. Gandhi's administration discouraged close ties between Indian servicemen and both their Russian and American counterparts. The respective governments tightly regulated Indo-Soviet military collaboration, focusing solely on technical guidance for Indian servicemen without any political influence. According to a Soviet official, Indian officers were seen as consistently maintaining a bourgeois mindset (Drieberg, 1974).

India's Foreign Policy Shifts:

The Soviet Union prioritized strengthening military ties with India. Concerned about India's exploration of diverse defense options, the Soviet Army Chief Pavlovsky visited India soon after Gromyko's departure. Subsequently, in July of the same year, the Indian Naval Chief visited Moscow, resulting in substantial gains for the Indian Navy, including the acquisition of two 'Kashin' class destroyers, five Ka 25 helicopters, and two M 38 maritime reconnaissance aircraft. Additionally, India agreed to purchase 70 T-72 medium tanks, collectively enhancing the Indian Navy's capabilities significantly (Sindhu, 1985).

2.2 Indo-Soviet Political Relations (1980-1991)

Significant political developments between India and the Soviet Union marked the period from 1980 to 1991. This era saw the deepening of strategic ties, economic cooperation, and political alignment, influenced by the broader context of the Cold War and internal dynamics within both nations.

The Soviet invasion of Afghanistan in 1979 did strain relations temporarily as India had to balance its non-aligned stance with its strategic partnership with the USSR. However, India's response was largely muted, reflecting its dependency on Soviet military and economic aid. India's diplomatic strategy involved supporting peace initiatives without directly condemning Soviet actions, thus maintaining a delicate balance (Ramachandran, 1983).

Economic ties between India and the Soviet Union deepened during this period, driven by extensive bilateral trade agreements and economic cooperation frameworks. The Soviet Union became one of India's largest trading partners, with trade agreements focusing on machinery, consumer goods, and raw materials. The 1980s saw the establishment of several joint ventures and cooperative projects in sectors such as steel, heavy machinery, and energy. For instance, the Bokaro Steel Plant and the Bhilai Steel Plant were significant symbols of Indo-Soviet economic collaboration (Mansingh, 1994). These projects not only facilitated technology transfer but also contributed significantly to India's industrialization efforts. The rupee-ruble trade agreement was a cornerstone of their economic relationship, allowing India to circumvent hard currency constraints and facilitating easier trade terms. This unique trade mechanism bolstered economic ties and ensured a stable flow of goods and services between the two nations (Malone, 2011).

Impact of the Afghan Conflict

India's muted response to the Soviet intervention in Afghanistan reflected its strategic calculus. India needed Soviet support to counterbalance Pakistan, which was receiving substantial military and economic aid from the United States and China. Moreover, the Soviet Union's assistance was crucial for India's defense and economic development. Therefore, India chose to pursue a policy of cautious engagement, supporting peace initiatives without jeopardizing its strategic partnership with the USSR (Raja Mohan, 2003).

Beyond military cooperation, the 1980s witnessed significant economic and technological collaboration between India and the Soviet Union. The two countries engaged in extensive trade agreements, which facilitated the exchange of goods, technology, and expertise. The Soviet Union became one of India's largest trading partners, with bilateral trade encompassing machinery, consumer goods, and raw materials (Malone, 2011). One of the most notable aspects of this economic relationship was the rupee-ruble trade agreement. This arrangement allowed India and the Soviet Union to conduct trade in their respective currencies, bypassing the need for hard currency and mitigating the impact of global currency fluctuations. This trade mechanism ensured a stable and predictable flow of goods and services, benefiting both economies (Sahadevan, 2002).

End of the Cold War and Transition

The late 1980s and early 1990s were marked by significant global transformations, with the Cold War coming to an end and the Soviet Union undergoing major political and economic changes under Mikhail Gorbachev's leadership. The policies of Glasnost (openness) and Perestroika (restructuring) introduced by Gorbachev had profound implications for Indo-Soviet relations (Raja Mohan, 2003). The dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991 marked a critical juncture in the bilateral relationship. The newly independent Russian Federation and other successor states sought to redefine their foreign policies and economic systems. For India, this transition presented both challenges and opportunities. India had to navigate these changes carefully, ensuring that it could continue to benefit from the strategic and economic advantages secured during the Soviet era (Mansingh, 1994).

India responded to these changes with pragmatism. It quickly established diplomatic relations with the Russian Federation and other former Soviet states. While the nature of the relationship evolved, the legacy of strong Indo-Soviet ties provided a robust foundation for continued cooperation. The strategic partnership with Russia, in particular, remained a cornerstone of India's foreign policy, with both countries continuing to collaborate on defense, trade, and technology (Malone, 2011).

The late 1980s and early 1990s were marked by seismic shifts in global politics as the Cold War drew to a close. This period witnessed the collapse of the Soviet Union and the end of bipolarity in international relations. Under Mikhail Gorbachev's leadership, the Soviet Union embarked on ambitious political and economic reforms known as Glasnost (openness) and Perestroika (restructuring). These policies aimed at democratizing the political system and revitalizing the Soviet economy but ultimately contributed to the dissolution of the Soviet state (Raisa, 2002).

Gorbachev's Reforms and Their Impact

Mikhail Gorbachev's policies of Glasnost and Perestroika, introduced in the mid-1980s, were designed to address systemic issues within the Soviet Union. Glasnost aimed to increase transparency in government institutions and promote freedom of information, which was a significant shift from the previously closed and secretive Soviet regime. Perestroika sought to restructure the Soviet economic and political systems, introducing elements of market economics and reducing the control of the Communist Party (Gorbachev, 1987).

India, which had relied heavily on the Soviet Union for military, economic, and diplomatic support, faced a challenging transition. The Indo-Soviet Treaty of Peace, Friendship, and Cooperation, signed in 1971, had been a cornerstone of India's foreign policy, ensuring a steady flow of military supplies, technological transfers, and diplomatic backing. With the dissolution of the Soviet Union, India needed to reassess its strategic partnerships and navigate the uncharted waters of a post-Cold War world (Raja Mohan, 2003).

Strategic Realignments and Challenges

The post-Cold War era required India to navigate a complex and rapidly changing geopolitical landscape. While maintaining its strategic partnership with Russia, India also sought to diversify its foreign relations. This period saw India improving ties with the United States and other Western nations, reflecting a pragmatic approach to its foreign policy. The end of the Cold War also meant that India could no longer rely on the bipolar structure of global politics to balance its regional adversaries, particularly China and Pakistan. This necessitated a more nuanced and multifaceted approach to international relations, where India sought to engage with multiple global powers to secure its strategic interests (Raja Mohan, 2003).

The early 1990s were also a period of significant economic reform within India. Under the leadership of Prime Minister P. V. Narasimha Rao and Finance Minister Manmohan Singh, India embarked on a path of economic liberalization, opening up its economy to foreign investment and reducing regulatory barriers. These reforms had a profound impact on India's foreign policy, making economic diplomacy a key component of its international relations (Malone, 2011). Economic liberalization allowed India to engage more effectively with the global economy and attract foreign investment. This shift was reflected in India's foreign policy, where economic considerations increasingly influenced diplomatic engagements. The relationship with Russia also adapted to this new economic paradigm, with both countries exploring new avenues for trade and investment, particularly in sectors such as energy and technology (Sahadevan, 2002).

The Economic Aspect of the Indo-Soviet Relationship

The Indo-Soviet treaty, primarily focused on political and security aspects, also underscored a vital economic dimension. This section emphasized the importance of economic, scientific, and technological collaboration between the two nations, emphasizing equality, mutual benefit, and most favored nation treatment. Starting from the mid-1950s, the Soviet Union significantly contributed to India's industrial development through state-owned enterprises. For India, the USSR provided crucial resources, capital, technology, and a substantial market for both traditional and newer exports.

Fig. 4 International North-South Transport Corridor[[INSTC](#)]

However, this long-standing and advantageous partnership faced challenges. A significant issue arose due to the differing developmental stages of the involved nations—one being highly developed and a superpower, while the other was a developing yet influential nation among emerging countries. This gap often raised concerns about unequal bargaining power in their economic ties, potentially disadvantaging India. Furthermore, internal dissent in India was evident regarding the rupee-rouble exchange rate used for trade between the two nations. This method received criticism from various quarters within India and international economic institutions like the IMF and GATT for its adverse impact on the weaker trading partner and global trade stability. Nevertheless, India defended its use, citing its role in strengthening ties with Moscow (Zimmerman, 1969).

Soviet Indian Trade: Trends and Challenges

The foundation of the economic ties between India and the Soviet Union rests on trade. Over the span of 1970 to 1985, there was a significant surge in bilateral trade, marking an eight-fold increase when measured in roubles and an eleven-fold rise when measured in rupees. Both inbound and outbound trade saw significant growth. India's exports to the Soviet Union surged from a mere 1.15 crores in 1953-54 to Rs. 644.65 crores in 1979-80, constituting 17.6% of the share by 1985-86. Likewise, India's imports from the Soviet Union increased from Rs. 0.60 crores to Rs. 728.60 crores in the same timeframe, accounting for 8.5% of the share by 1985-86 (Hahn, 1982) India's initial trade pact with the Soviet Union was established in December 1953, marking the country's inaugural long-term trade agreement with another sovereign nation since gaining independence. Subsequently, two additional agreements were formed by the end of the 1960s. However, these agreements proved insufficient to significantly boost trade. Later agreements extended over longer periods and incorporated improved strategies for bilateral trade, emphasizing industrial cooperation to foster trade expansion and collaboration within Third World nations.

Technology Sharing

The Soviet Union played a crucial role as a primary technology provider across various fundamental industries crucial for India's developmental strategies. Initially, they took the lead in aiding India in establishing numerous pivotal projects, notably in sectors like steel, fertilizer production, refineries, and mining. The essence of the economic and technological collaboration between India and the Soviet Union centered on creating modern industrial facilities in vital economic sectors. These endeavors significantly contributed to India's pursuit of economic autonomy. According to the 1977-78 MEA Report, a standout characteristic of the Indo-Soviet economic ties was the Soviet's readiness to support India in essential economic sectors, fostering self-sufficiency, encompassing steel, heavy machinery, power generation, pharmaceuticals, and more. In subsequent years, India began seeking technological aid from alternate nations due to a change in its industrial production trend. The reliance on the Soviet Union for technology diminished, prompting India to diversify its sources for technology transfer, moving beyond arms supplies. Consequently, during 1980-1981, India's portion of the overall economic and technical support provided by the Soviet Union decreased, albeit maintaining the second-highest position after Mongolia. This decline was affirmed by data from the Soviet side (Sahni, 1991).

The Private Sector and Soviet Union in India during 1971-1991

India's economic policy during the period from 1971 to 1991 was characterized by a mixed economy model, with a blend of state control and private enterprise. The government played a dominant role in key sectors such as heavy industries, infrastructure, and finance, while allowing for the existence of a private sector, particularly in areas like agriculture, small-scale industries, and services. One of the key features of India's economic policy during this period was the system of industrial licensing and regulation. The government exercised strict control over the establishment and expansion of industries through a licensing regime, which aimed to prevent the concentration of economic power in private hands and ensure equitable growth (Chandra, 2008).

India adopted an Import Substitution Industrialization (ISI) strategy during the 1970s and 1980s, aiming to reduce dependence on imports by promoting domestic industrialization. This strategy involved the creation of a protective tariff regime, subsidies for domestic industries, and state-led investment in key sectors (Ghosh, 1994).

The Soviet Union also provided financial assistance to India through credit facilities and economic aid packages. These funds were utilized for various purposes, including infrastructure development, industrial projects, and defense procurement. However, the terms of this assistance often required India to align its economic policies with Soviet interests, including restrictions on private sector growth. Despite the dominant role of the state, the private sector in India experienced some growth during the 1970s and 1980s. Small and medium enterprises (SMEs), in particular, played a significant role in sectors such as manufacturing, trade, and services. However, the private sector faced numerous constraints, including bureaucratic red tape, regulatory hurdles, and limited access to credit and resources (Kohli, 2004).

Aspects of Indo-Soviet Defense and Strategic Relations

India's reliance on its Soviet ties has been most significant in the realm of defense. It stands as the foremost non-aligned beneficiary of Soviet weaponry. Between 1974 and 1985, the worth of these arms amounted to roughly \$6.8 billion in present-day value and \$8.7 billion when adjusted for inflation in the United States (Brozoska, 1987). SIPRI's records indicate that between 1982 and 1986, approximately two-thirds of the Soviet shipments to the Third World were directed to three specific treaty partners: Syria, Iraq, and India. Among these partners, India held the second-largest share of Soviet exports at 20.3%, trailing behind Syria, which accounted for 24% of the total Soviet exports during that period (Bhatt, 1989).

The supply of Soviet goods to India had a qualitative dimension. Starting from the late seventies, there was a remarkable enhancement in the quality of weaponry India received from the Soviet Union. India was granted cutting-edge Soviet equipment, often ahead of their allocation to the Warsaw Pact nations. The quantity and quality of Soviet arms transferred to India strongly signaled a robust and enduring relationship in this sensitive domain. However, when evaluating this relationship concerning India, other factors played a significant role. India's defense strategy, articulated in successive Ministry of Defense reports, consistently centered on attaining self-sufficiency in defense manufacturing. This approach was seen as the sole viable method to reduce India's reliance on external powers for armaments. For instance, the 1980-81 report proposed an ambitious plan to phase out imported technology within a span of 10 to 15 years (Bose, 1985).

Dependency on Soviet Arms

In contrast to Pakistan's swift pursuit of arms to recover from its losses in the 1971 war, India, being firmly established as the dominant power in the region, initially lacked the urgency to adopt a similar approach. However, as Pakistan's rapid rearmament raised concerns among India's defense strategists, the situation changed. SIPRI observed a notable decrease in Soviet arms supplies to India in 1972, with no orders placed for Soviet equipment in 1972-73. This decline, according to SIPRI, might not signify a significant policy shift but rather the completion of deliveries, including SU-7 fighters and other key equipment, by the Soviet Union during that period (Chowdhury, 1974). During the evaluation period, India's Defense Ministry established fundamental principles for the country's defense strategy following an analysis of the prevailing strategic landscape.

Diversification of Major Arms: Testing the Strength of the Indo-Soviet Military Connection

In March 1978, the Soviet Deputy Defense Minister and Air Chief Kautakhov presented a new proposal, offering improved credit and manufacturing terms, estimating a cost of Rs.2.5 crores. Despite this, the Indian Government maintained its initial stance, citing that the MiG-23 failed to fulfill the technical and operational requirements of the Indian Air Force. India is currently engaged in ongoing discussions with both the USSR and Western nations regarding the acquisition of a DPSA. India opted for an "outright purchase" of 25% of its total aircraft requirement from the British, while the rest would be produced within India through licensed manufacturing, as outlined in the Defense Ministry's report. During a media briefing held on

October 1st, 1978, the Defense Minister of India denied claims regarding the contemplation of a Soviet MiG-23 (Pajak, 1981).

Sustaining Strong Indo-Soviet Military Ties Amidst Western Diversifications

Rajiv Gandhi embraced a contemporary and scientific perspective. He seemed drawn towards the Western world, particularly the USA, acknowledging their superior advancements in modern technology and cutting-edge weaponry compared to the Soviet Union. His alignment with the West was aided by the evolving US stance towards India, aiming to steer India away from the Soviet Union by demonstrating friendliness and extending support in vital domains. The USA's official statement acknowledges India as a dominant force in the region, possessing the capacity to build a strong military presence. This capability could impact the strategic interests of the US in the area, either positively or negatively (Chishti, 1990).

Mikhail S. Gorbachev's shift in Soviet political thought prompted a reevaluation of the Soviet approach to Third World nations, significantly impacting the country's arms transfer policy to these regions. Unlike Brezhnev, who enthusiastically championed national liberation movements in these countries and the Soviet involvement in them, Gorbachev, during the 27th CPSU Congress, exercised caution. Rather than fully committing the Soviet Union to these liberation movements, Gorbachev opted to express support for the struggles against imperialism in these nations. He emphasized that the primary responsibility for constructing a new society lay with the nations themselves, refraining from extensive Soviet involvement in their liberation movements (Government of the USSR, 1976)

Publishing endeavors by the Soviet Union in India

The Soviet desire to share their culture and perspectives took a concrete shape through foreign-language publishing initiatives. India notably embraced Soviet books and magazines, becoming the largest consumer of Soviet print outside the socialist bloc in the 1970s. This enduring popularity is evident today in the revered status of Soviet literature, especially the beautifully illustrated children's books.

According to him, India's alignment with Soviet cultural philanthropy was due to its strong communist parties, its constitutional commitment to a form of socialism, and its leadership in the non-aligned movement, which inclined towards the Soviets. Soviet-produced materials in India were broadly categorized into two groups: first, books and magazines that were translated and published in the Soviet Union, later distributed in India through a network of local publishing houses and bookshops; and second, materials printed within India, often by the Information Department of the Soviet Union's Embassy there. The Soviet publishing industry had distinct characteristics on a global scale. The volume of published books and magazines was remarkable and unmatched by any other nation. According to Gregory Walker, an expert in Soviet book publishing, approximately 300,000 individuals were involved in the machinery of Soviet publishing, printing, and book distribution (Boškowska, Fischer-Tinè, & Miškovič, 2014).

3. Conclusion

3.1 Indo-Soviet Political relations

- The Indo-Soviet Treaty of Friendship and Cooperation (1971) was a pivotal document strengthening political, military, and economic ties between India and the Soviet Union, significantly reshaping the regional balance of power in South Asia.
- Strategic and defense collaboration between the two nations bolstered India's military capabilities, with the Soviet Union becoming a key supplier of advanced weaponry and technological transfers, enhancing India's defense infrastructure.
- Despite cooperation, the Soviet intervention in Afghanistan in 1979 created tension, as India maintained a stance against intervention, highlighting differences in regional conflict approaches but not severing broader cooperation.
- Cultural, economic, and technological exchanges deepened the relationship, with trade agreements and economic aid from the Soviet Union contributing to India's economic stability, particularly during Indira Gandhi's tenure.
- Post-1991, following the end of the Cold War and India's economic reforms, the Indo-Soviet relationship evolved into a more diversified partnership with Russia, shifting towards strategic cooperation, trade diversification, and diplomatic engagements.

3.2 Indo-Soviet Economic Relations

- The Indo-Soviet economic relationship, initially rooted in political and security cooperation, evolved to include economic, scientific, and technological collaboration, significantly contributing to India's industrial development from the mid-1950s onward.
- Bilateral trade between India and the Soviet Union grew substantially from 1970 to 1985, but challenges emerged due to disagreements over crude oil, pricing issues, and currency adjustments, alongside India's decreasing dependency on Soviet supplies.
- Shifts in the 1970s and 1980s, including India's move toward economic liberalization and the Soviet Union's perestroika reforms, introduced new economic strategies, yet Indo-Soviet economic ties remained crucial.
- Soviet aid was essential in advancing India's public sector and industrial projects, particularly in steel, refineries, power, and mining, although India gradually diversified its technology sources and sought Western partnerships.
- Despite changes in global and domestic economic dynamics, the Indo-Soviet collaboration laid the foundation for continued economic cooperation, reflecting evolving geopolitical and economic realities.

3.3 Indo-Soviet defense and Strategic Relations

- Between 1971 and the late 1970s, India heavily relied on Soviet arms for its military growth, especially in the navy and air force, despite initially aiming for self-sufficiency. Concerns over Soviet influence in defense policy arose but did not compromise India's autonomy.
- The Janata Government's decision to procure the Anglo-French Jaguar over the Soviet MiG-23 marked a shift towards diversifying India's arms sources to reduce overreliance on the Soviet Union, driven by factors like technology suitability and economic viability.

- The Soviet intervention in Afghanistan influenced regional defense strategies, with India securing a major \$1.6 billion arms deal from the USSR to balance U.S. arms aid to Pakistan. India's procurement of Mirage 2000 from France reflected its efforts to diversify arms suppliers.
- Despite efforts to diversify arms procurement, India maintained strong ties with the Soviet Union, balancing Moscow's sophisticated weaponry offerings with its strategic non-aligned policy and regional security concerns.
- During the Gorbachev-Rajiv Gandhi era, India sought advanced Western technology but remained primarily reliant on the USSR for arms due to financial reasons and concerns over U.S. reliability, despite facing challenges with Soviet spare parts and outdated weaponry.

3.4 Indo-Soviet Cultural relations

- The Indo-Soviet Cultural Society (ISCUS) and other friendship societies emerged to foster cultural ties between India and the Soviet Union, playing a key role in cultural, scientific, and academic exchanges.
- ISCUS's trajectory was shaped by political dynamics, especially the influence of the Communist Party of India (CPI) and its relationship with the Congress and Indira Gandhi's government, which led to internal conflicts and the formation of competing organizations.
- The Soviet Union's intervention in Afghanistan in 1979 strained Indo-Soviet relations, as India distanced itself from the conflict while maintaining overall diplomatic ties with the USSR.
- Cultural initiatives, including Soviet publishing efforts, cinema collaborations, and Indo-Soviet literature exchanges, significantly influenced Indian cultural landscapes, spreading Soviet ideologies through translated literature and media.
- Despite the vibrant cultural ties, political shifts in the 1980s and changing global dynamics led to a decline in the influence of Indo-Soviet friendship societies, as India sought to diversify its international relationships.

References

1. Bajpai, U. S (1982). *India's Security - The Politico-Strategic Environment*. New Delhi, India: Lancer International.
2. Bhatia, V (1984). *Indo-Soviet Relations: Problems and Prospects*. New Delhi: Panchsheel Publisher.
3. Bhatt, G. D (1989). *Indo-Soviet Relations and India's Public Opinion*. Delhi: Pacific Publication.
4. Bhattacharya, D (2009). *India-Soviet Union Relations: From Nehru to Gorbachev*. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, 44(1), 75-92.
5. Bose, T.C (1986). *Reagan Administration's Foreign Policy: The Indian Dimension*. In S. Kumar (Ed.), *Yearbook on India's Foreign Policy 1983-84* (pp. 169-184). New Delhi: Sage Publications.

6. Boškowska, N., Fischer-Tinë, H., & Miškovič, N Eds.) 2014). *The Non-Aligned Movement and the Cold War*. New York: Routledge.
7. Chandra, R 2008). *Indian Economy: Performance and Policies*. New Delhi: McGraw Hill Education.
8. Chaulia, Sreeram 2012). "India and the Soviet Union: A Study of Military Cooperation (1971-1991)." *Journal of Strategic Studies*, 35(4), 553-570.
9. Chishti, S 1990). *Indo-Soviet economic relations*. In S. Kumar (Ed.), *Yearbook on India's Foreign Policy, 1987-88* (pp. 143-155). New Delhi: Sage Publication.
10. Driberg, T., et al 1974). *Towards Closer India-Soviet Cooperation*. Delhi: Vikas Publishing House.
11. Dutt, V. P 1984). *India's Foreign Policy*. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House
12. Ganguly, S 2002). *Conflict Unending: India-Pakistan Tensions Since 1947*. New York: Columbia University Press.
13. George, T., Litwak, R., & Chubin, S 1984). *India and the Great Powers*. Hampshire International Institute for Strategic Studies (USS), Gower Publishing House.
14. Ghosh, J 1994). *The Process of Financial Liberalization in India*. New Delhi: Sage Publications.
15. Gorbachev, M 1987). *Perestroika: New Thinking for Our Country and the World*. Harper & Row.
16. Kohli, A 2004). *State-Directed Development: Political Power and Industrialization in the Global Periphery*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
17. Malone, D. M 2011). *Does the Elephant Dance?: Contemporary Indian Foreign Policy*. Oxford University Press.
18. Mansingh, S 1984). *India's Search for Power: Indira Gandhi's Foreign Policy 1966-1982*. New Delhi: Sage Publication.
19. Mishra, G 1977). *Contours of India-Soviet economic cooperation*. Delhi, India: Allied Publishers
20. Mukherjee, S 2017). *India's Cultural Diplomacy: A Study of the Soviet Union*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
21. Novosti Press 1971). *24th Congress of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union (30 March-9 April 1971) Documents*. Moscow.
22. Pajak, R. F 1981). *Soviet arms transfer as an instrument of influence*. *Survival*, 23(4), 165-173.
23. Panagariya, A 2008). *India: The Emerging Giant*. New York: Oxford University Press.
24. Pant, H. V 2009). *India's Role in Global Affairs: An Overview*. New Delhi: Pearson Education India.
25. Raisa, Y 2002). *The Fall of the Soviet Union: The End of an Empire*. Random House.
26. Raja Mohan, C 2003). *Crossing the Rubicon: The Shaping of India's New Foreign Policy*. Penguin Books India.
27. Ramachandran, S 1983). *India-Soviet Relations: Some Reactions*. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 18(36), 1529-1530.

28. Sahadevan, P 2002). India and Soviet Union: Trade and Economic Relations (1953-1991). Radiant Publishers.
29. Sahni, V 1991). Technology Transfer and India-Soviet Cooperation. New Delhi: Lancer Books.
30. Sarin, R 2013). India's Foreign Policy in Afghanistan (1979–1989): A Study in Regional Dynamics. New Delhi: Pentagon Press.
31. Sindhu, K.S 1985). Studies in Indian Defence. New Delhi: Harnam Publisher
32. Singh, K 2014). Indo-Soviet Economic Relations: A Historical Perspective. International Journal of Social Economics, 41(9), 752-768.
33. Vajpayee, A. B 1978). Continuity and change in India's foreign policy. New Delhi: Ministry of External Affairs.
34. Whelan, J. G 1984). The Soviets in Asia: An expanding presence CRS Report No. 84-118F). House Foreign Affairs Committee.
35. Zimmerman, W 1969). Soviet perspectives of international relations, 1956-67. Press.

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